

THE ANALYSIS OF THE RELATION AMONG JOB SATISFACTION, SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION, COLLEAGUES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TEACHERS IN TERMS OF GENDER

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Abstract:

This research was conducted to examine the relationships between physical education and sports teachers and their colleagues, the support of the school administration to them and the level of job satisfaction they feel about their profession in terms of gender variation. The sample of the research, done by using the general survey model, constituted of a total of 108 teachers, 79 males and 29 females, working in the central district of Malatya province and selected randomly. The scales of colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction components were used as data collection tools in the research. Based on the answers given to the scale by the teachers in the sample, it was determined that the general arithmetic mean of the scales was moderate level in terms of the positive scores of the components from all the gender groups. According to the arithmetic scores, it was determined that female teachers felt more positive colleague-school administration support and job satisfaction perception compared to male teachers according to the variables of marital and education status and working time. In addition, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between male teachers' education and marital status and working time variables and arithmetic scores of the components. For female teachers, it was found that married female teachers had a significant difference in the school administration support, single teachers in job satisfaction, and there was no significant difference in other variables and components.

Keywords: colleague relations, school administration, job satisfaction, physical education and sports teacher

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1. Introduction

Job satisfaction can be expressed as the general attitude that an employee has shown towards his job (Cetinkanat, 2000). Job satisfaction is a mixture of emotional, cognitive and behavioral components just like other attitudes (Eser, 2010). It is not a different concept from the general meaning and it is expressed that it is related to the fulfilling of the requirements (Avsaroglu, Deniz and Kahraman, 2005).

One of the important factors affecting the work environment is colleague relations (Arslan, 2006; Basaran, 2008). Employees who have a positive relationship with their colleagues, who support team spirit, and who have colleagues with appropriate worldviews are reported to have a high level of job satisfaction by researchers (Bozkurt and Bozkurt, 2008; Yilmaz, 2007). In addition, the employees who stated that their job satisfaction is high, also stated they would own their work more and produce better quality products in a work environment where human relations are at the highest level, technical competence is high and open to cooperation (Bingol, 2003). It is stated that the employees who do not have such environments feel themselves alone in the social sense and may face negative situations such as decreased motivation and increasing stress level and not enjoying their work (Bozkurt and Bozkurt, 2008). Employees in a high quality interaction with their supervisors may be inclined to have higher job satisfaction (Ozutku, 2007). Communication can be defined as transferring of knowledge, emotions and opinions by fulfilling the elements of communication (Sabuncuoglu and Tuz, 2008). The concept of elements of communication is a subject that needs to be carefully considered in organizations. Effective management is also based on a good communication process (Eser, 2010).

In this context, communication is the basic foundation for organizations to survive and realize their goals (Elma and Demir, 2000). For this reason, administrators should create a psychological environment to enable two-way communication in working environments (Sabuncuoglu and Tuz, 2008). Employees' easily access to their administrators gives important clues about the adequacy of organizational communication. Administrators keeping the communication channels available and allowing the operation of the communication process will provide an open and effective communication process (Yuksel, 2005).

When managers appreciate the employees for the work they have done as a means of promoting in the work environment, it can be said that it is an important indicator in terms of showing that managers support the work being done and reward their employees for their performance. The previous research show that one of the factors affecting the job satisfaction of the employees is appreciation, and it is stated that

the appraisal is the foremost of the ways leading to the success of the employees (Eser, 2010). The job satisfaction of an employee who is timely and appropriately appreciated due to his/her effort will be affected by this situation (Basaran, 2008; Bozkurt and Bozkurt, 2008). The research conducted previously indicates that appraisal is a tool desired by the employees and increasing their confidence (Arslan, 2006).

2. Method

The present research was conducted to examine the colleague relationships of physical education and sports teachers, the support of the school administration and the level of job satisfaction they feel about their profession in terms of gender variation. The general survey model was used in the research. The general survey method is a survey method that will be performed on all of the population or on the sample taken from it in order to make a general judgment about the population in an environment composed of a large number of elements (Karasar, 1984).

The population of the research constitutes of 260 permanent physical education and sports teachers working in Malatya province center during the 2014-2015 education period (Provincial National Education Directorate, 2014). The sample consists of a total of 108 physical education and sports teachers, 79 males and 29 females, who are working at different schools and randomly selected. In descriptive research, when the fact that the number required for large populations is at least 20% (Arli and Nazik, 2001) is taken into consideration, it can be said that the number of the sample represents the population.

In order to collect data necessary for research, job satisfaction (Oranje, 2001; Magill, 2002), colleague relations (Oranje, 2001) and school administration support scales (Magill, 2002), which were adapted to Turkish by Ozgun (2005) were used (Transf. Eser, 2010). The scales aim to determine job satisfaction, colleague relations and school administration support level in five-point Likert type. The responses of the athletes participating in the research to the scale items according to the demographic variables were calculated by means of a statistical package program.

Descriptive statistics, frequency, percentage, standard deviation, arithmetic mean, t-test and one-way variance analysis were used in the research. The level of statistical significance Alpha (α) error level was accepted as $p < 0.05$. The results obtained from the distributions were tabulated, the findings were interpreted, and the necessary solutions were proposed.

The option ranges and a general evaluation of the scales used in the research are calculated as follows (Sarigoz, Hacicaferoglu, Donger, Cam, Koca, 2015;Hacicaferoglu, 2015).

$$CR = \frac{MaxV - MinV}{NoC} = \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,8$$

		1.00 - 1.79:	Low Level
CR:	Choice Range	1.80 - 2.59:	Below Medium Level
MaxV:	Maximum Value	2.60 - 3.39:	Medium Level
MinV:	Minimum Value	3.40 - 4.19:	Above Medium Level
NoC:	Number of Choices	4.20 - 5.00:	High Level

3. Findings

In this section, statistical findings on the data obtained from the physical education and sports teachers were included.

Table 1: Descriptive findings related to teachers by gender variable

Components	Gender	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	t-	p
Colleague Relations	<u>Male</u>	79	73.4	2.95	.51	106	-587	.558
	Famale	29	26.6	3.01	.31			
	<i>Total</i>	108	100	2.96	.46			
School Administration Support	<u>Male</u>	79	73.4	2.75	.98	106	-1.088	.279
	Famale	29	26.6	2.98	.81			
	<i>Total</i>	108	100	2.81	.94			
Job Satisfaction Situation	<u>Male</u>	79	73.4	2.90	.32	106	-823	.412
	Famale	29	26.6	2.96	.29			
	<i>Total</i>	108	100	2.92	.31			

According to gender variables, there was no statistically significant difference ($p > .05$) between perception levels of male and female teachers on colleague associations, school administration support and job satisfaction.

Table 2: Descriptive findings of male and female teachers
 according to marital status variable N = 108

Components		MaritalStatus	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	t-	p
Male	Colleague Relations	Bachelor	14	17.7	2.94	.43	77	-.087	.931
		Married	65	82.3	2.95	.53			
	School Administration Support	Bachelor	14	17.7	2.90	1.12		.628	.532
		Married	65	82.3	2.72	.95			
	Job Satisfaction Situation	Bachelor	14	17.7	2.97	.39		.858	.394
		Married	65	82.3	2.89	.30			
Female	Colleague Relations	Bachelor	5	17.2	2.96	.57	27	-.348	.731
		Married	24	82.8	3.02	.24			
	School Administration Support	Bachelor	5	17.2	2.17	1.27		-2.707	.012
		Married	24	82.8	3.14	.59			
	Job Satisfaction Situation	Bachelor	5	17.2	3.23	.54		2.408	.023
		Married	24	82.8	2.90	.19			

It was identified that there was no statistically significant difference ($p > .05$) in perception levels felt from colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction in connection with marital status variable according to gender variable.

Table 3: Descriptive findings of male and female teachers
 according to education status variable N = 108

Components		Education	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	t-	p
Male	Colleague Relations	Undergraduate	70	88.6	2.94	.51	77	-.412	.682
		Post Graduate	9	11.4	3.01	.52			
	School Administration Support	Undergraduate	70	88.6	2.74	.96		-.371	.711
		Post Graduate	9	11.4	2.87	1.15			
	Job Satisfaction Situation	Undergraduate	70	88.6	2.89	.33		-.807	.422
		Post Graduate	9	11.4	2.99	.15			
Female	Colleague Relations	Undergraduate	22	75.9	2.96	.32	27	-1.296	.206
		Post Graduate	7	24.1	3.14	.24			
	School Administration Support	Undergraduate	22	75.9	3.03	.83		.605	.550
		Post Graduate	7	24.1	2.81	.78			
	Job Satisfaction Situation	Undergraduate	22	75.9	2.94	.32		-.591	.559
		Post Graduate	7	24.1	3.02	.19			

According to education status variable, there was no statistically significant difference ($p > .05$) between perception levels of male and female teachers on colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction.

Table 4: Descriptive findings of male and female teachers
 according to working years variable N = 108

Components	WorkingYears	Male Teachers						Female Teachers					
		N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	F	p	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	F	p
Colleague Relations	1-5 years	6	7.6	2.86	.59	.752	.524	2	6.9	3.00	.70	1.352	.280
	6-10years	40	50.6	3.01	.44			14	48.3	3.08	.27		
	11-15 years	25	31.6	2.84	.54			5	17.2	2.76	.09		
	16-20 years	8	10.6	3.06	.71			8	27.6	3.04	.34		
School Administration Support	1-5 years	6	7.6	2.83	1.25	.956	.418	2	6.9	3.28	1.41	.459	.713
	6-10 years	40	50.6	2.92	1.03			14	48.3	3.11	.79		
	11-15 years	25	31.6	2.58	.90			5	17.2	2.88	1.16		
	16-20 years	8	10.6	2.41	.74			8	27.6	2.73	.53		
Job Satisfaction Situation	1-5 years	6	7.6	2.86	.31	.288	.834	2	6.9	3.07	.46	.719	.550
	6-10 years	40	50.6	2.91	.28			14	48.3	2.92	.36		
	11-15 years	25	31.6	2.93	.32			5	17.2	2.86	.19		
	16-20 years	8	10.6	2.90	.48			8	27.6	3.08	.13		

There was no statistically significant difference ($p > .05$) between male and female teachers who participated in the study and the years they worked in the profession, colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction perception level.

4. Discussion

According to the analysis results of the data, it was determined that the general arithmetic means of the colleague relations, the school administration support and job satisfaction perceptions of the male and female physical education and sport teachers participating in this research are moderately close to each other. Therefore, it can be said that perceptions from the colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction components of married and single teachers are equal, but as arithmetic scores, female teachers have more job satisfaction, school administration and colleague support compared to male teachers. Perception levels not being higher can be interpreted as male and female physical education and sports teachers often working in schools where there is no physical environment in which they can perform their lectures, especially the lack of support from school administrators and colleagues at competent level compared to other branch teachers in the preparation of sports branches. This may cause male and female teachers to feel anxious about their profession (Hacicaferoglu, Hacicaferoglu, Secer, 2015). When the related research is examined; it is seen that there are results indicating male teachers feeling more satisfied

compared to female teachers (Aydoğan, 2011; Aydoğan ve Bas, 2016; Avsaroglu, Deniz and Kahraman, 2005; Demato, 2001; Hacicaferoglu, Hacicaferoglu, Selcuk, 2016). On the other hand, research results indicating that female teachers have more job satisfaction than male teachers as arithmetic scores can also be seen (Carikci, 2004; Yilmaz and Ceylan, 2011). However, Hacicaferoglu and Hacicaferoglu (2013) stated that the job satisfaction scores of male and female participants are close to each other.

In the studies applied to different professions, it has been concluded that men are happier in the environment they work (Aydoğan, 2016) and that they can continue their happiness with sporting activities and thus decrease their occupational burnout situations (Ozturk, 2010). Hacicaferoglu, Gundogdu and Hacicaferoglu (2012/a-b) have found that students who are prospective teachers at universities are not able to get enough support from school administrators to develop themselves professionally. In universities, which are the first step in achieving the professional objectives of physical education or other prospective teachers, administrators must cooperate with each other or with instructors (Hacicaferoglu, 2014/a; Hacicaferoglu, BozkusKizilkaya, 2014). Teachers should read books and similar materials that will improve their communicative and professional skills before they start to teach professionally, especially during their university years (Karatas, Korkmaz, Yucel, Hacicaferoglu, Atalay, 2015). Universities are important institutions where individuals' cultural, artistic and sportive developments are supported, intellectual accumulation is used in real life, and individuals gain a new perspective on life (Atalay, Akbulut, Karatas, Hacicaferoglu, Yucel, 2015).

In this context, it can be said that all the students studying at universities need to take courses that are about the psychological and sociological dimensions of cultural, artistic and sportive developments in the curriculum (Hacicaferoglu, Selcuk, Hacicaferoglu, Karatas, 2015) and that students should be engaged in spare time activities which will help learners achieve these objectives (Hacicaferoglu, Gundogdu, Hacicaferoglu, Yucel, 2014). It can be stated that these activities will enable students to have a healthy, happy, moral, and balanced personality and to manage the adverse situations that they may encounter in their future professional life (Basoglu, 1995; Hacicaferoglu, 2014).

Administrators and instructors must be in contact with prospective teachers in order to make them gain terminal behaviors and to provide them with professional competence (Hacicaferoglu, 2014/b). A previous study on sportsmen shows that effective communication is an important factor in increasing the performance of the athletes (Hacicaferoglu, Hacicaferoglu, Selcuk, Karatas, 2013; Hacicaferoglu, Korkmaz, Atalay, Yucel, Koksall, 2015), which supports our argument.

It was identified that there is no statistically significant difference of perception levels of colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction in connection to marital status variable according to gender variable. Therefore, it can be said that perceptions from the colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction components of married and single male teachers are equal. It was determined that married and single female teachers have no statistically significant differences in colleague relations, and that there is a significant difference between school administrative support and job satisfaction components. In this case, it can be said that the perceptions of married and single female teachers in colleague relations are equal, and married teachers have more perception of school administration, and single teachers have more perception of job satisfaction according to arithmetic scores. In some research on the subject, it is seen that this perception changes between these components (Altinkilic, 2008; Arslan, 2006; Canbay, 2007; Duman, 2006; Girgin, 2009; Ozturk, 2013).

According to education status variable, there is no statistically significant difference between perception levels of male and female teachers on colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction. In this case, when the groups of teachers are examined, it can be said that female teachers who have received post-graduate education in arithmetic sense perceive these components more positively. Employees with higher levels of education are more closely related to productivity and have developed less negative feelings towards their work; in other words, these employees are more concerned with the quality of their work performance and they do not complain about work-related elements (Yelboga, 2007).

Bilir's (2007) and Gergin's (2006) studies on the related subject indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between participants' education variables and colleague relations, manager support and job satisfaction levels. However, there are study results stating that there is a statistically significant difference in favor of postgraduate teachers in the sub-dimension of colleague relations (Karakaya, Hacicaferoglu ve Kilinc, 2014).

There is no statistically significant difference between male and female teachers who participated in the study and the years they worked in the profession, colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction perception level. Therefore, it can be said that perceptions from the colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction components of teachers in groups showing the years of work in the profession are close, but female teachers have more positive perceptions from these component with more scores compared to male teachers. In addition, it was determined that male and female teachers with more seniority have more positive

perceptions from colleague relations and job satisfaction components, whereas male and female teachers with less seniority have positive perceptions from school administration support. In this case, it can be said that the participants with a longer seniority are more mature in age better with their colleagues and their working order is in routine, and they have no problematic environments. It is seen in the research of Arslan (2006), Altinkılıç (2008), Karatas, Gundogdu, Yucel, Hacicaferoglu, Karadag, Hacicaferoglu, (2012), Karakose and Kocabas (2006) and Yilmaz and Ceylan (2011) that they reached a conclusion close to the results of the current research. On the other hand, in the study by Eser (2010) and Schultz and Schultz (1998), it was determined that teachers with less seniority are more satisfied than those with more seniority.

5. Conclusion

As a result, it was determined that the general arithmetic mean of the scales is close to each other by colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction levels related to their professions are moderate, based on the responses to the answers given by male and female physical education and sport teachers who participated in the research. According to the arithmetic scores, it was determined that female teachers have more positive colleague-school administration support and job satisfaction perception compared to male teachers according to the variables of marital and education status and working time. In addition, it was found that there is no statistically significant difference between education and marital status and years worked in profession variable and colleague relations, school administration support and job satisfaction. For female teachers, it was found that married female teachers have a significant difference in the school administration support, single teachers in job satisfaction, and there is no significant difference in other variables and components.

6. Recommendations

For sports to be internalized by individuals as a profession or leisure activity, it is important that the sports education is given at a young age to provide more positive results. In this context, physical education and sports teachers should be able to educate the amateur and professional athletes or to make the students gain sports habits supporting their future lives, full support regarding the negative situations they may encounter in school environments should be given by other branch teachers and school administrators, without discriminating male or female teachers, during the application of lessons of physical education and sports. Based on this situation, the viewpoints of

teachers and administrators on physical education and sports lessons should be positive. In order to ensure a positive change in this direction, to make the specialists support physical educators and sports teachers and thus to increase the awareness, in-house seminars should be given to the teachers and administrators in the provincial and district national education directorates.

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